

Impacts of Climate Change and transmission of Malaria in poor States of India

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Abstract: Climate change and climate variability will likely aggravate public health disparities, in which malaria is great cause of concern. According to World Malaria Report, 2022 released by WHO, indicated that India accounted for 79% of cases and 83% of deaths because of malaria in the South- Eastern Asian region. The report has also indicated presence of mutations in Central India. The mutations may have relations with drug resistance along with climate variability. Research is needed, particularly in vulnerable poor States of India, to predict the expected impacts. The objective of the paper is to study the impacts of climate change and transmission of malaria in poor States of India with special focus on State of Uttar Pradesh. World Malaria Report, 2019 published by WHO indicate that seven States account for nearly 90% of the burden of malaria cases in India. These are Uttar Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, West Bengal, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh and Odisha. These cases are primarily in those areas which are facing poor sanitation conditions, malnutrition, pollution and shortage of clear drinking water. A universal recommendation developed as improved and accessible medical health services, identification of vulnerable areas, improved surveillance and integration of climatic variations while working parallelly to implement adaptation mechanisms. The research can be used in addition to the ongoing programs of government to control malaria and to reduce the vulnerability of people towards parasitic diseases such as malaria under the future climate projections.

IndexTerms - Climate Change, Malaria, Land-use pattern, Population Migration

I. INTRODUCTION

Malaria, a vector borne disease, has been an issue in India for centuries. Mention of vector borne disease and its details can be found in ancient Indian literatures like Atharva- Veda and Charak Samhita. In early nineteenth century, malaria cases were widespread in India which turned to one- fourth of Indian population in later part of nineteenth and twentieth century (Malaria in India – Malaria Site, n.d.). Malaria in India is especially prevalent in the north- eastern, eastern and central part of country. This is due to factors such as hilly and forest region, drainage problem, conflict affected area with inadequate access to health infrastructure, multiethnicity & low community awareness among tribal and marginal population and inadequate access to health infrastructure. Even in low malaria transmission states, majority of the malaria cases are confined to areas with above eco-epidemiological scenario. These areas are also influenced by continuous influx of migrant people from neighboring endemic areas and bordering countries (Malaria in India: Statistics & Facts | Severe Malaria Observatory, n.d.).

To overcome the problem of malaria cases and deaths, Indian government had launched the National Malaria Control Programme in 1953 which was changed with some modification to ambitious National Malaria Eradication Programme in 1958. Though in the initial phases of the program, the cases dropped sharply but later on cases started rising again with repeated setbacks (Dash et al., 2008).

Climate change refers to change in shifts of average temperature and other meteorological data. The causes and repercussions of climate change is constantly spreading in breadth and depth. Though low- and middle-income countries are relatively less responsible and has contributed very small percentage in greenhouse gas emission but since these low- and middle-income countries are facing high level of poverty as about 90% of global population live under extreme poverty conditions (Alkire et al., n.d.).

The adverse health impact associated with climate change will likely impact these people who are under extreme poverty conditions. High risk areas are those areas which are experiencing resource scarcity, environmental degradation, risk of infectious diseases, weak infrastructure and overpopulation. In particular tropical zones will experience significant health impact due to climate change (Sattenspiel, 2000). Changing meteorological parameters especially temperature and rainfall pattern will further

affect health because of breeding of vector borne disease carriers and its transmission, such as malaria, dengue, chikungunya, Kala-azar and elephantiasis (Dhiman, 2008).

The goals of the research paper to briefly summarize relevant literature, highlight the enormous challenges and opportunities for innovative research with particular focus on poor State of India. This research will help in finding an unseen link of climate change with transmission of these vector borne diseases and pave the path for unique and pioneering solutions.

The relationship of climate change with transmission of malaria in Odisha State was studied by Ruchi Singh Parihar, where the author projected the future malaria transmission in highly endemic region of India i.e., Odisha through numerical simulations. Though there may be other factors involved in transmission of malaria but this paper focuses mainly on the relationships with meteorological data especially temperature and rainfall.

Climate change and impacts of malaria in poor States of India-

World Malaria Report, 2019 has shown that malaria drop is sharpest in India but the concerning issue is 90% of malaria are concentrated in seven States of India (Telling Numbers: Malaria Drop Is Sharpest in India, 90% of Cases Are in 7 States | Explained News, The Indian Express, n.d.-a). These States are Jharkhand, Uttar Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, West Bengal and Gujarat. On microscopic level observation, it can be concluded that malaria prone States are either those which have relatively high tribal population or facing high level of poverty. According to the report 228 million cases have been reported globally; in which more than 85% of the cases are from semi- tropical or tropical countries i.e., African region and India. WHO region wise recorded highest malaria cases in Africa which is nearly 93% of total cases followed by south- east Asia, east Mediterranean and western Pacific. Though decline in cases have been recorded in all region except in western Pacific.

In another study, it has been concluded that climate hazards such as flood, drought and heat-wave lead to 58% of infectious disease (Study Connects Climate Hazards to 58% of Infectious Diseases, n.d.). According to the study 218 out of 375 human infectious diseases are having connect with climate change. In some cases, flooding and downpours sicken people through vector borne diseases.

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), in its sixth assessment report on “Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability” warned malaria outbreak in Himalayan regions (Langsdorf et al., 2022). According to the report, transmission of vector borne disease is projected to expand to higher latitudes and altitudes. Climate change is projected to increase the transmission of malaria geographical distribution in sub- Saharan and southern Africa, Asia and South America. Study has shown that higher temperature combined with land- cover/ land- use change is making areas suitable for spreading of vector borne diseases. Climate change and its variability are facilitating spread of malaria in southern and eastern Africa, chikungunya in central, north and south America, Asia as well in Europe and dengue globally. The report has also highlighted that future global burden of climate sensitive disease will depend on adaptation pathways and efficiency of public health system and sanitation measures. Projections were made under mid-range emission scenario show that additional 2,50,000 deaths annually by 2050 compared to 1961- 1990 due to malaria, childhood undernutrition and heat.

United Nations in its report on “Climate change and malaria” has identified mosquito affected regions as Africa, Asia and Latin America mainly which account for approximately 1 million deaths and nearly 1 billion new cases (Nations, n.d.). The report shows the variability of climate condition and the profound effect on the breeding condition and longevity of mosquito and malaria transmission. Elementary modelling has suggested that climate change has increased the transmission of vector borne disease and has widened the endemic geographical affected regions. The study has also highlighted that climate change has not only spread the transmission of vector borne diseases but has also re- emerged the diseases in the areas which have controlled the transmission cases or has eliminated the cases. Though climate change has also been faced in the developed countries of Europe including Scandinavian countries but these countries have not faced re-emergence of malaria cases. The reason behind the control of the cases is better socio- economic conditions, clean drinking water facilities, adoption of farming methods, better health care and behavioral change. The report has also highlighted complexity of relationship between climate change and malaria and existing gaps in knowledge in the mechanism of linkage, as it is function of many parameters like population and demographic dynamics, insecticide resistance drug resistance, and other human activities. Climate change influence the EL Nino cycle and thus increase in temperature and precipitation will proliferate the malaria cases in high altitudes and high latitudes. The report has recommended surveillance and preparedness, with special focus on developing countries to control the malaria cases.

In another paper by Sumana Bhattacharya in “Climate change and malaria in India” argued the influence of climate change on vector borne diseases and malaria transmission in India (Bhattacharya et al., 2006). Climate change has been analyzed on the basis of regional analysis and a relation has been made with incidence of malaria cases. The paper concluded that central and eastern Indian regions have emerged as the most endemic malarious regions covering Madhya Pradesh, Jharkhand, Orissa, Chhattisgarh, Assam and West Bengal in the current climate conditions. Numerical projections have been done and it has been projected that malaria is likely to persist in Orissa, West Bengal and southern parts of Assam, bordering north of West Bengal. Though, it may shift from the central Indian region to the south western coastal states of Maharashtra, Kerala and Karnataka. Also, the northern states, including Himachal Pradesh and Arunachal Pradesh, Nagaland, Manipur and Mizoram in the northeast may become malaria prone. The duration of the transmission windows is likely to widen in northern and western states and shorten in the southern states. The report has also highlighted that the extent of vulnerability due to malaria depends on the prevailing socio-economic conditions. The increase or decrease in malaria threat due to climate change in the 2050s will therefore depend on the development path followed by the country. Therefore, it is important to understand the current adaptation mechanisms and improve the coping

capacities of the vulnerable section of the population by helping to enhance their accessibility to health services, improved surveillance and forecasting technologies.

Risks of malaria epidemics in relation to El Niño and Southern Oscillation (ENSO) events have been mapped and studied at global level. In India, where malaria is a major health issue, no such effort has been undertaken that inter-relates El Niño, monsoon rainfall (ISMR) and malaria (Dhiman & Sarkar, 2017). The study has been done to find out the relationship between ENSO events, rainfall and intra-annual variability in malaria cases in India. The study concluded that there exists a relationship between El- Nino and malaria transmission specially in States of Orissa, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Bihar, Uttarakhand, and parts of Madhya Pradesh. The study has also pointed that a more detailed and comprehensive study at regional level is required for better understanding of the relationship, and generating a forewarning tool to mitigate and control of malaria outbreaks in India.

The scope of the problem and current research: Poverty and malaria threat-

Many of the forecasted impacts of climate change are going to be reality in India. India is very diverse geographically, meteorologically as well as culturally. The world's second most populous country represents 1/6th of global population, support 1/50th of global land and 1/25th of global water (Agarwal et al., 2006). With a huge population and haphazard developments, climate change poses a threat that will magnify health threats. Millions of the people below poverty line and those in rural areas represent high health risks due to poor sanitation, pollution, shortage of clean drinking water and malnutrition. However, awareness and development of health infrastructure can negate the burden of climate related disease.

India has approximately 2 million confirmed cases of malaria annually; but the concerning issue is these cases are concentrated in poor States of India. WHO concludes that approximately 15000 individuals die from malaria each year in India (Health Organization, n.d.). Though the data has some problem for backward and poor States like Uttar Pradesh because malaria is easily mistaken with other life-threatening diseases. Mostly in backward areas, death due to malaria is common because of lack of medical infrastructure and inaccessibility to medical healthcare system. These cases make difficulties in research to find a relationship between climate change and malaria transmission as there will be difficulty to find hospital-based data.

In India 90% of the malaria cases are reported from seven States (Telling Numbers: Malaria Drop Is Sharpest in India, 90% of Cases Are in 7 States | Explained News, The Indian Express, n.d.-b). In Odisha, the disease has much more seriousness in terms of its transmission, though the State has improved in health infrastructure to reduce the malaria deaths commendably. The emergence of drug resistance has further aggravated the problem (Kumar et al., 2007). Another issue of vector borne disease is; malaria in urban area due to rapid urbanization and peri- urban environment, traditional methods to store water, water management and rapidly rising poverty level.

The need for adaptation-

Malaria is a major health problem in parts of country about 95% people in country reside in malaria endemic areas and 80% of the malaria cases are reported in the country is concentrated in the areas of tribal, hilly, difficult and inaccessible areas. (MAGNITUDE OF THE PROBLEM: National Center for Vector Borne Diseases Control (NCVBDC), n.d.). Many developed countries have eliminated malaria. Recently 12 countries including China, Sri Lanka (Health Organization, n.d.). India has also adopted substantial attention in elimination of malaria cases. In this direction, National Framework for Malaria Elimination 2016- 2030 was launched by central government in 2016 with a vision to eliminate malaria by 2030. This will contribute in improved health, quality of life and alleviation of poverty. The framework has clearly defined objectives, goals, targets and strategies to eliminate malaria in a phase wise manner (India - Government and Public Donors - The Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria, n.d.).

Transmission of malaria and its relation with climate change need adaptations towards climate change also. It will occur at physiological, behavioral, institutional, social and organizational scales. To focus more on the malaria endemic poor areas a baseline understanding of the region is important in terms of demography, social and ecological determinants of health. Moreover, for better health responses, factors like age structure, socio- economic profile, prevalence of climate sensitive diseases, public awareness, available public health services and climate impact on health should be considered (Ezzati et al., 2006). Furthermore, adaptation strategies in terms of climate variability and modification in existing programs with respect to projected impact of climate change will make adaptation strategies more effective. This will add more social and environmental sensitive education and sanitation. To make the adaptation process smooth communities affected by impacts of climate change should be involved to enhance human and technical capacity both at local and national level (Mearns & Norton, 2010). Failure to invest now will likely increase the severity of consequences in the future (Haines et al., 2006).

Recommendations

Environmental monitoring- there is a need to improve environment monitoring system in low- and middle-income countries like India. Research needs to be done on collection of long-term high-quality data on climate and related health outcomes. Research needs focus on both current scenario of climate- health outcomes and future predictions. Surveillance of weather conditions and indicators such as mosquito abundance is also important. Such data need to be integrated with the ongoing health programs and schemes. Areas where basic health facilities are missing need to be integrated with such facilities. This will help the researcher to work towards finding out relationship between climate and health and will also help in designing way outs.

Data Collections- Though malaria and other vector borne diseases are medical problems but geography helps in figuring out the causes behind cases and concentration of case in a specific area. Spatial analysis and Geographic Information System (GIS) helps

in conducting vulnerability assessments, environmental exposure assessment and transmissions of cases. Social data from census, surveys and data from GIS can be used altogether to find the sensitivity and adaptive capability of region. Data on land-use pattern, urbanization and land-cover can also be used to assess the risk and vulnerability.

Such special information and data on Human- Environment interaction can be used to assess the vulnerability spatially as well as temporally through integration of such socio- economic and environmental data. This is a very effective tool when predicting prevalence, targeting resource distribution and designing control programs for infectious disease such as malaria (Ageep et al., 2009).

Behavioral change and capacity building- For these recommendations and analytical techniques to be effective human need to enhance their behavior and build their capacity for risk communication. This will aware people about climate change and will integrate the unseen relationship of climate with health to run more holistic health programs and government schemes such as region and area specific climate action plans.

Other factors- A country like low and middle income like India need to work in infrastructure building, improvement in medical health facilities, need to ensure greater accessibility to medical health services. Along with that vulnerable zone identification, surveillance and monitoring system need to be developed and integrated. An integrated plan for environment management needs to be developed. An important part will be public awareness and local participation in awareness campaign without which the pace of malaria elimination will be slow.

Conclusion

Malaria is one of the major issues in public health. India carries 2% of global malaria cases and 2% of malaria deaths. The country has improved significantly towards malaria control. In 2020, India has improved 57% in terms of malaria cases and 56% in malaria deaths (Malaria in India: Statistics & Facts | Severe Malaria Observatory, n.d.). National Framework for Malaria Elimination 2016-2030 has been launched to eliminate malaria by 2030 which has its objectives to improve health, quality of life and alleviation of poverty.

Researches on climate variability and human health has great heterogeneity. This heterogeneity is due to difference in research design, difference in socio- economic status and availability and accessibility to medical health services. Moreover, this heterogeneity is so strong that the results for one region is tough to extrapolate to another region. Therefore, it is recommended to develop a comprehensive data catalogue of climate variation and associated health outcomes. Better understanding of the relationship can be achieved through studies specific to climate change and populations.

India has done tremendously as part of action against climate change. In 2008, National Action Plan on Climate Change was launched to make development path sustainable and environment friendly. Moreover, India declared Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and has taken it seriously and made binding on itself. Thus, there is no doubt, India has tremendous opportunity and action plans regarding sustainable development and adaptation techniques to climate change. But the real challenge is to make a relationship of climate change with human health. World scientists and policy makers have tried to find the relationship in different malaria burdened countries worldwide; especially in African countries. The same attention and research need to be done in Indian perspective as well. Adoption and initiation of these studies will provide the necessary tools and techniques to develop scientific questions and development design to the complex issue of climate change.

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